

HARDNESS CRITICAL APPRECIATION OF HIGH DENSITY FIBREBOARD (HDF) IN ECONOMY OF NIGERIA

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Abstract: Technical information on hardness test analysis on high-density fibreboard (HDF) in Nigerian economy needed by stakeholders to prevent loss of revenue that may arise due to choice of indecorous high-density fibreboard (HDF) for plentiful demands as a result of absence of such data was scrutinized. Identified and subjected to test to establish their hardness were the top three most frequently sought after high-density fibreboard (HDF) in Nigerian market. The samples were tested four times on the machine and the mean determined after they were prepared as required by the Leeds Hardness Tester. From the generated data, plots on the hardness of the samples were ensued by computer program. Results show that Dabar attained aggregate average hardness of 526.50 Leeds Hardness Test (HLD), Joubert attained aggregate average hardness of 548.50 HLD while Sinoply attained aggregate average hardness of 547.50 HLD. Quantitatively, that of Joubert is 0.18% and 4.18% harder than Sinoply and Dabar respectively. Sinoply is also 4.00% harder than Dabar. It is worthy to note that the difference in hardness between Joubert and Sinoply which is 1.00 HLD is small compared to the difference in hardness between Joubert and Dabar which is as much as 22.00 HLD. Preference of high-density fibreboard (HDF) with respect to their hardness potentials from Nigeria market depending on application should rely on this novel technical data. This unique knowledge should be valued by architects, building contractors, engineers, individuals, construction companies as well as furniture makers even as biomedical engineers should leverage on it for the development of their designs. Forthcoming research works in wood composites should focus on warping challenges in wood composites.

Keyword: Leed Hardness Test, Material Hardness Testing, Material Testing, Mechanical Testing, Rockwell Hardness Test, Scleroscope Testing.

I. Introduction

Background of the Study

In Nigeria, wood composite remains a vital engineered wood product as it is extensively used across construction, furniture, and packaging industries. Despite abundant raw materials and a fast-growing domestic market, it is unfortunate that Nigeria presently remains heavily dependent on plywood imports. FMRL, (2025) noted that the global plywood market valued at USD 50.2 billion in 2024 is expected to grow from year 2025 with projection to reach USD 74.5 billion by the year 2033 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) estimate of 4.5%. Nigerian plywood market valued at USD 8.81 billion in 2023 is expected to grow at a CAGR of 3.3%, reaching USD 11.05 billion by 2030, (FMRL, 2025). Once enjoyed by Nigeria was the forestry products industrial goods exports in the 1950's, 1960's and 1970's, (Ogunwusi, 2012). Normally obtained through the processes of binding the particles, strands, boards, or fibers of wood together, wood composites, a derivative of wood product. While helping facilitate optimal processing conditions, similar composite products can also be made from vegetable fibers using lignin-containing materials with chemical additives enabling the integration of polymer and wood flour. Particle and fiberboards usually made of materials like rye and wheat straw, sugar cane residue, hemp stalks e.t.c, are widely used in the building industry as eco-friendly solutions to wood with increasing uses in thermal insulators, ceiling boards, wall partitions, e.t.c. due to an excellent combination of mechanical, thermal and acoustic properties together with a competitive price, (Garcia-Garcia, et al, 2018). Engineered to certain specifications resulting in a material that can have diverse applications, wood composites are achieved by the use adhesives. Wood composites can be created by the use of smaller trees, wood waste materials and hence it is of interest to note the reduction in the need to fell old-growth forests. Study of the production of highly environmentally-friendly fiberboards by hot-press molding using *Posidonia oceanica* wastes and a partially biobased epoxy resin as binder showed that there is a remarkable improvement of the mechanical properties with combination of the alkali treatment followed by silanization, (Garcia-Garcia, et al, 2018). Despite these advantages when wood composite is compared to solid wood products, higher fire hazards could be experienced due to higher chemical heat content and melting properties of composites. Toxic formaldehyde is usually released from the finished products forming a strong apprehension with wood composite use when mostly cheap and commonly used resins in the composites are usually made with urea-formaldehyde bonded products. As it relates to solid timber demands for extra primary energy in the process of their manufacture, wood composites have numerous advantages. Some fiber-based and particle based composite woods when they are exposed to moisture experience humidity-induced warping which is not common in solid woods. The demand for wood composite is interestingly noted to be on the rise as projected by the earlier statistics despite all these challenges stated due to remarkable improvement on esthetic and mechanical properties of the resulting composites. In a revelation that the economy especially building materials market was badly hit by the inflation, the purchasing power of the Nigerian currency Naira in the study of inflation trend pattern and its impact on Nigeria's economy expectedly was seen to be decreasing, (Barguma, et. Al. 2022). A very strong relationship has been found to exist between building materials prices and rate of residential development when the effect of building materials cost on housing development in Owerri, Imo state, eastern region of Nigeria was assessed, (Igboekulie, Monye, and Joseph, 2022).

The inflation rate and the prices of building materials in Benin city, was analyzed from a correlation analysis and it showed that inflation was the most influential factor responsible for increase in the cost of building materials with the prices of the building materials having a direct relationship with the inflation rate in Nigeria thus the cause for the high cost of building materials, (Obaedo, 2024). The obvious need and advantages of wood composites orchestrate this research in high-density fibreboard (HDF) in Nigerian economy.

Hardness of Material and Testing

Processes employed to determine a material's resistance to scratching, indentation or even deformation, are procedures to establish the materials hardness. To ascertain the actual resistance exhibited by materials to permanent deformation, the test is usually conducted by penetration of another harder material. As a mechanical test for material properties, material hardness testing is used in structural analysis, materials development and engineering design and development. This is achieved by pressing a harder material into the surface of the tested material. The depth which is basically the size of the resulting indentation is measured and subsequently converted into a hardness value, shows how well the material can resist deformation that is permanent. Brinell Hardness Number (BHN) is calculated from the measured diameter of the indentation when a hardened steel or carbide ball indenter is used to create an indentation on the surface of the material being tested. Barcol Hardness Test is mainly used to provide quick and easy measurement for very soft materials like plastics. Employed over a wide range of materials from very soft to very hard ones by the use of a square-based diamond pyramid indenter is Vickers Hardness Test. A rhombic-based diamond pyramid indenter is often used for thin films and brittle materials in Knoop Hardness test and Vickers Hardness Test. Shore Durometer measures the hardness of rubber and plastics with the use of a spring-loaded indenter while the Scleroscope measures hardness by the rebound height of a diamond-tipped hammer that is dropped onto a material. A dynamic impact test, Leed Hardness Test that measures the rebound of a small impactor (indenter) to determine the hardness (HLD) is dopted in this research.

II. Literature Review

Eze, Ilo and Dim, (2025) noted that results of material hardness tests on medium density fibreboard in Nigerian economy show that Hokusan attained aggregate average hardness of 535.75 Leeds Hardness Test (HLD), Richard Russel attained aggregate average hardness of 545.75 HLD while SGK Nordiac attained aggregate average hardness of 558.50 HLD. According to statistics, that of SGK Nordiac is 2.34% and 4.25% harder than Richard Russel and Hokusan respectively. In an attempt to find the relationship between age and properties of timber (Ojo and Idieunmah, 2021), established linear relationship between age and strength properties of timber, increasing both the compression and shear strengths and even to a reasonable extent the bending strength. Iloabachie, et al, (2017) found that maximum flexural and ultimate tensile strength were attained at 20wt% for the 425 microns sample when the effect of particle size on the flexural strength, ultimate tensile strength, density and water absorption characteristics of uncarbonized coconut shell/unsaturated polyester composites of particle size 425 microns sample and 170 microns sample were investigated. When the effect of adding a blend of tannins to commercial urea formaldehyde (UF) on the particleboard made from wood

particles of *Acacia seyal* var. *seyal* using the British Standard European Norm (BSEN) relevant standards as compared to the ones produced by solely urea formaldehyde (UF) was investigated, high mechanical properties were found, (Elbadawi, et al, 2015). Flexural strength and elongation at break increased as coconut shell proportion got increased upon the study of the effects of carbonized coconut shell (CS) volume fraction on mechanical properties of unsaturated polyester resin (UPR) composite, (Iloabachie, Obiorah and Anene, (2018). By simple methodology of just increasing the percentage of (CNSL), tensile strength of Teak Wood Saw Dust – Cashew nut shell liquid resin composites was studied by preparing a composite material using a hand layup technique by varying the quantity of the Cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) resin and keeping the saw dust quantity constant. The tensile strength of the sample with the highest percentage of (CNSL) was seen to be the highest and that the tensile increased with increase in (CNSL), according to the ASTM D638, (Ganesan and Valarmathi, 2014). This reveals that the tensile strength of the composite is improved with the increase in the cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) percentage. Coconut fibre reinforced HDPE has 28.6 mega pascal as optimum value for flexural strength when performance characteristics and reinforcement combinations of coconut fibre reinforced high density polyethylene (HDPE) polymer matrixes at optimum condition of volume fractions and particle sizes of coconut fibre-filler was studied, (Ihueze, Achike, and Okafor, 2016). The tensile strength, face screw holding and modulus of rupture meet the minimum specifications of the US standards when both physical and mechanical properties of WPC evaluated in a study conducted to test for the potentials of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) such as plastic films from packaging as resins for saw dust from coconut lumber for the production of wood-plastic composite (WPC) particleboard when the boards were prepared from 50%-80% by weight of LPDE to sawdust content, (Valle, 2020). Good interfacial adhesion between sawdust particle and LDPE reduced thickness swelling and improving moisture resistance by diminishing hygroscopy hence expanding the utilization of composites from agricultural wastes and plastic wastes for industrial applications, especially in moist environments, even as well as marine use and humid environment was also revealed by the study. Carbonized coconut shell particle reinforced composite recorded the least density value making it desirable in light weight material application when the effects of carbonization on the physical and mechanical properties of coconut shell particle reinforced polyester composite was studied, (Iloabachie, et al 2014). Both physical and mechanical properties, the panels with 50% CC had the most preferred performances when the properties of developed composite corn cob (CC) and sawdust (SD) particle boards using 100%, 75%, 50%, 25% and 0% variations for both agricultural wastes using formaldehyde as binder at constant volume was studied, (Akinyemi. Afolayan, and Oluwatobi, 2016). Okafor, Ihueze, and Nwigbo, (2013) showed that empty fruit bunch fibre reinforced polyester matrix composite has the maximum hardness strength of 19.062 N/mm² which depended greatly on the reinforcement combinations of control factors upon the optimization of hardness strengths response of plantain fibres reinforced polyester matrix composites (PFRP) by application of Taguchi robust design. Courard, et al, (2012) noted that changes were observed on surface quality after 50 reuses with oriented strand board (OSB) panels formworks while modification of surface quality was noticed after 80 reuses with marine plywood formworks when critical evolution of surface properties of concrete through measured

lightness and absorption was analysed in the study of panel formworks. Ozioko, (2011) revealed that wear behaviours of 9500C carbonized ash were better than those of 8500C and 9000C carbonized ash due to the degree of alteration in the structure of silica upon the analysis of the effect of carbonization temperature on wear rate behaviour of rice husk ash reinforced epoxy composites. The values in glulam beams are significantly higher than the control (custom wood) especially in edgewise direction when assessment of the flexural strength of glued laminated beams made from local wood species bonded with phenol resorcinol formaldehyde, polyurethane and urea-formaldehyde adhesives was made, (Ekundayo, Arum and Owoyemi, 2022).

Conclusively, it is obvious that from the reviewed literature with regards to their hardness that research has not been directed towards providing technical information on hardness of high-density fibreboard (HDF) in Nigerian economy, hence the need for the study.

III. Research Methodology

Material

Commonly used and major high-density fibreboard (HDF) in the Nigerian economy was investigated on. From the survey made, most common and three high-density fibreboard (HDF) in top demands in Nigerian market were identified. They were selected as samples for analysis. The high-density fibreboard (HDF) samples were Dabar, Joubert and Sinolpy. Accordingly, the samples are in table 1.

In table 1, the samples are coded “x”, “y” and “z” representing Dabar, Joubert and Sinolpy respectively. One after the other, they are all prepared according to the requirement by the machine and tested on the machine.

TABLE 1 High-Density Fibreboard (HDF) Samples Tested

Sample	x	y	z
Make	Dabar	Joubert	Sinolpy

The materials under investigation as marked in the table 1 are shown in figure 1 below.

Fig. 1: High-Density Fibreboard (HDF) tested

Equipment

The Leeds hardness tester, a portable non-destructive machine for measuring hardness as seen in figure 2 which is a type of dynamic hardness test machine was used. Working on the rebound velocity of usually a small impact body which is the indenter after it strikes the surface of the material, the data generated is recorded. The indenter pushes to make an indent on the sample as the indenter is placed on each sample and device gadget clicked. Set carefully according to the requirement by the Leeds hardness tester in figure 2, the samples (x) representing Dabar, (y) representing Joubert and (z) representing and Sinolpy were all tested on the machine successively. As the Leeds hardness tester is operated by placing the indenter of the Leeds hardness tester on the sample and clicking the control button, the indenter pushes forward to make an impact on the sample by indenting on it. Repeated four times for each sample (make) for an average, the operation cycle is completed for the sample. The Leeds hardness (HLD) plots are generated with computer program, following the dynamics of the action of the indenting and the associated resistance. Being a function of the sample's composition resulting from their nature, the plot clearly shows the relationship between force per unit area and the extent of the impact (indent) in the sample. Under Results and analysis below, the plots generated are discussed.

Fig. 2: Leeds Hardness Tester.

IV. Results and Analysis

For each of the samples Dabar, Joubert and Sinolpy, the results of the tests are shown as plots in figures 3, 4 and 5 respectively. Essentially, the hardness test results in HLD are for the tested samples of the three selected high-density fibreboard (HDF).

Plots

The figure 3 below is a plot for hardness test result of Dabar sample. The first test recorded 562 HLD, the second recorded 496 HLD, the third recorded 533 HLD while the fourth recorded 515 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests is taken and reported in the figure 6 for a comparative analysis.

Fig 3: Graph of Hardness Test Results for Dabar in HLD.

The figure 4 below is a plot for hardness test result of Joubert sample. The first test recorded 499 HLD, the second recorded 534 HLD, the third recorded 595 HLD while the fourth recorded 566 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests is taken and reported in the figure 6 for a comparative analysis.

Fig. 4: Graph of Hardness Test Results for Joubert in HLD.

The figure 5 below is a plot for hardness test result of Sinolpy sample. The first test recorded 537 HLD, the second recorded 568 HLD, the third recorded 547 HLD while the fourth recorded 538 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests is taken and reported in the figure 6 for a comparative analysis.

Fig. 5: Graph of Hardness Test Results for Sinoply in HLD.

The figure 6 below is a plot for aggregate average of the four hardness tests result on the samples. Dabar recorded 526.50 HLD, Joubert recorded 548.50 HLD while Sinoply recorded 547.50 HLD.

Fig. 6: Graph of Aggregate Average of Hardness Test Results for Dabar, Joubert and Sinoply in HLD.

V. Conclusion and Recommendation

Hardness test results shows that Dabar achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 526.50 HLD, Sinoply achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 547.50 HLD while Joubert achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 548.50 HLD. In comparison, Joubert is 0.18% and 4.25% harder than Sinoply

and Dabar respectively. Sinoply is also 4.00% harder than Dabar. The results are as revealed from the tests. The implication is that Sinoply is harder than Dabar while Joubert is harder than Sinoply. It is worthy to note that the difference in hardness between Joubert and Sinoply is small compared to the difference in hardness between Joubert and Dabar which is as much as 22.00 HLD. Choice of high-density fibreboard (HDF) with respect to their hardness potentials from Nigeria market depending on application can leverage on this novel technical data. This unique knowledge should be valued by architects, building contractors, engineers, individuals, construction companies as well as furniture makers even as biomedical engineers should leverage on it for the development of their designs. Future research works in wood composites should focus on warping challenges in wood composites.

REFERENCES

- Akinyemi. B. A., Afolayan, J. O. and Oluwatobi, E. O. (2016). Some properties of composite corn cob and sawdust particle boards. *Construction and Building Materials* 127, 436-441.
- Barguma, W. S., Atanda, B. T., Chidiebere, U. E, Kudirat, B. F., and Busola, T. R. (2022). A Study of Inflation Trend Pattern and Its Impact on Nigeria's Economy. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 3(4): pp 5989-5997
- Courard, L., Goffinet, C., Migeotte, N., Martin, M., Pierard, J. and Polet, V. (2012). Influence of the reuse of OSB and marine plywood formworks on surface concrete aesthetics. *Materials Structures* (45): 1331-1343. <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-012-9835-0>
- Ekundayo, O. O., Arum, C. and Owoyemi, J. M. (2022). Bending strength evaluation of Glulam Beams made from selected Nigerian wood species. *International Journal of Engineering (IJE)*. (35)11: 2120-2129
- Elbadawi, M., Osman, Z., Paridah, T., Nasroun, T. and Kantiner, W. (2015). Properties of particleboards made from Acacia Seyal Var. Seyal using UF-Tannin modified adhesives. *Cellulose Chemistry and Technology*. 49 (3-4): 369-374.
- Eze, C.C., Ilo, C. P. and Dim, E. C. (2025). Hardness Appraisal of Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) in Nigerian Economy. *Top Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 1-12, September – October, DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17158069>. ISSN: 2994-0419. Available at: <https://topjournals.org/index.php/TMRJ/article/view/1029>, [Google Scholar Indexed].
- FMRL, (2025). Plywood manufacturing in Nigeria; The feasibility Report. <https://businessplansinnigeria.ng/business-plans/plywood-manufacturing-in-nigeria-the-feasibility-report/#:~:text=Since%201997%2C%20annual%20production%20has,%2C%20the%20UAE%2C%20and%20Austria.>

- Ganesan M. and Valarmathi T.N. (2014). Tensile Strength of Teak Wood Saw Dust – Cashew nut shell liquid resin composites. *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research* (www.ijedr.org) *IJEDR*. 2(1): 196-199. <https://rjwave.org/IJEDR1401034.pdf>
- Garcia-Garcia, D, Quiles-Carrilo, L., Montanes, N., Fombuena, V. and Balart R. (2018). Manufacturing and Characterization of Composite Fibreboards with *Posidonia oceanica* wastes with an Environmentally-Friendly Binder from Epoxy Resin. *Materials*, 11(1): 35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma11010035>
- Igboekulie, I. E., Monye, C. and Joseph, F. F. (2022). Assessment of the effect of building materials cost on housing development in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)*, 4(9): 455-474, DOI: 10.35629/5252-0409455474
- Ihueze, C. C., Achike, M. K. and Okafor, C. E. (2016). Optimal performance characteristics and reinforcement combinations of coconut fiber reinforced high density polyethylene (HDPE) polymer matrixes. *Journal of Scientific Research & Reports*. 9(3): 1-10. Doi:10.9734/JSRR/2016/20385
- Iloabachie, I. C. C., Obiorah, S. M. O. and Anene, F. A. (2018). Study of mechanical properties of carbonized coconut shell polyester composite. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*. (13): 54-62
- Iloabachie, I. C. C., Obiorah, S. M. O., Ezema, I. C., Henry, V. I. and Chime, O. H. (2014). Effects of carbonization on the physical and mechanical properties of coconut shell particle reinforced polyester composite. *International Journal of Research in advanced Engineering and Technology*, 3(1), 62-69, www.engineeringresearchjournal.com.
- Iloabachie, I. C. C., Obiorah, S. M. O., Ezema, I. C., Okpe, B. O., Chima, O. M. and Chime, A. C. (2017). The effects of particle size on the flexural strength, tensile strength, and water absorption properties of uncarbonized coconut shell/polyester composite. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering and Technology*. (1)1: 22-27.
- Obaedo, B. O., (2024). The Inflation Rate and the Prices of Building Materials in Benin City, *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 4(4):1112-1122, DOI:10.62225/2583049X.2024.4.4.3158
- Ogunwusi, A. A. (2012). The Forest Products Industry in Nigeria. *An International Multidisciplinary Journal, Ethiopia*. 6(4), Serial No. 27. Pp191-205. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/afrev.v6i4.13>

- Ojo, O. S. and Idieunmah, F. M. (2021). Influence of Age on the Strength of Different Species of Timber. *LAUTECH Journal of Civil and Environmental Studies*. (6)2: 39-46, DOI: 10.36108/laujoces/1202.60.0240.
- Okafor, E.C., Ihueze, C. C. and Nwigbo, S. C. (2013). Optimization of Hardness Strengths Response of Plantain Fibers Reinforced Polyester Matrix Composites (PFRP) Applying Taguchi Robust Design. *International Journal of Engineering*. (26)1: 1-11. Doi:105829/idosi.ije.2013.26.01a.01
- Ozioko, F. U. (2011). Effect of carbonization temperature on wear rate behaviour of rice husk ash reinforced epoxy composites. *Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practices and Technologies*, (19); 172-182, <https://lejpt.academicdirect.org>
- Valle, S. (2020). Evaluation of the potential of recycled LPDE and waste sawdust in wood in wood-plastic composite boards. *In the book: 2020 ISWA-SWIS Winter School Proceedings*. Solid waste Institute for Sustainability (SWIS), The University of Texas at Arlington